

THEORETICAL INTERPRETATION OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Jabborova Malohat Azimovna

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

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In the conditions of globalization, education plays an important role in the development of a person in all aspects, in the formation of perfection and the qualities characteristic of a qualified specialist. Today's fast-paced era demands to arm students with reasonable information in a short period of time, to create the necessary conditions for their thorough mastering of the basics of various subjects.

In modern conditions, the main goal of the educational process is to develop, socialize, and train independent, critical, creative thinking skills. When we analyze the historical development path of developed countries, we see that the attention given to youth education, science, and the development of new technologies in them was extremely huge. For this reason, consistent reforms are being implemented in the state policy of our country in order to give priority to the development of science, the education of young people, and the training of highly educated and qualified personnel.

Raising the educational system to a new level, increasing the quality of education and improving the assessment standards are currently the main issues in the focus of pedagogy and pedagogical psychology.

Among the issues that should be studied in the education system at the moment are the following: increasing the effectiveness of education, determining the relative content of the concept of "having a result" in all stages of education; search for methods of substantiation, selection, development and implementation of modern assessment tools suitable for educational goals, i.e. development of positive socialization and set of necessary competencies; issues such as creating conditions in which it is possible to predict the level of academic achievement of the student, as well as the stability of the level of efficiency throughout the education.

Academic mastery of students is a pedagogical criterion that means the level of completeness, depth, awareness and consistency of the knowledge, skills and qualifications they have acquired. Bringing students' learning to a high quality level in Uzbekistan is one of the most important tasks facing the national education system. Because intellectual development and professional preparation of students directly depends on their level of academic mastery.

"Educational result " also changes with the change of the requirements for the content of education at all levels of the education system. Learning outcomes are what students demonstrate in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes after completing the learning process.

Educational results in higher educational institutions can be current, intermediate and final, but still the term "result" itself means certain indicators. Therefore, in our research, we have a procedural meaning, i.e. "academic mastery", which describes and studies the effectiveness of learning, educational success, as well as the student's educational success. We also analyzed several terms of the subject: "educational achievement", "educational success", "educational efficiency", "academic success", "learning efficiency". The success of any student in learning and his achievements in the educational process are the determining indicators of educational results.

Academic means something related to learning (mainly at a university), meaning academic, theoretical. The origin of the term "academic" is related to the ancient Greek culture of education and training, which appeared in the VI-V century BC. Based on Plato's pedagogic position, "the main goal is not only science or professional education, but also individual education".

Educational efficiency in modern educational institutions is not only limited to educational results, but it has activity-practical, motivational, valuable and emotional aspects.

One of the most important conditions for achieving the educational result is the student's constant study. Through academic mastery, a student can demonstrate the stability or instability of the dynamics of academic activity. In the second half of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, many pedagogues and psychologists studied the level of mastery expressed by quantitative indicators (scores) of educational activity - that the quality of education is more reflected in the academic mastery of students it was emphasized¹.

"Academic mastering" as a scientific term is a recent introduction to scientific treatment. The famous Russian psychologist B.G. Ananyev² was one of the first researchers who spoke not only about the objective assessment of educational activity, but also about the subjective side of effectiveness.

¹Rubin Yu.B. *Sovremennoe obrazovanie: kachestvo, standardy, instrument* / Yu.B. Rubin. - 2nd izd. - Moscow: Market DS, 2009. - 330 p.

²Ananev B.G. *K psychophysiology of the student age // Sovremennye psychologicheskie problemy vysshey shkoly.* - L., 1974. -280 s.

Academic mastery is a subjective and objective state reflecting educational achievements (formalized, including the structure of learning outcomes, related to "knowing", "learning", "acquiring"). is not a complex feature.

Academic Mastery:

- reflects the diversity of the educational process;
- reflects the progress achieved in the process of preparation for education, as well as the process of achieving it;
- includes the stability or instability of the results shown by the students in the dynamics;
- includes conditions for achieving results;
- the student's reflects his opinion about what the educational outcome means for him and how far he has achieved it.

Many factors affect students' learning in higher education institutions : financial situation, health, age, family situation, level of preparation before university, self-organization skills, o adequacy of initial ideas about planning and control of one's activities (primarily, education), motivations for choosing, university, specific features of university education; form of education (day, evening, part-time, distance education, etc.), the existence of a payment contract and their amount, the organization of the educational process at the university, the material and technical base of the university, the level of education, the qualifications of teachers and staff, the reputation of the university, and finally, the individual psychological characteristics of students.

in any activity, including education, depends primarily on the level of intellectual development. The relationship between intellectual abilities and activity has a dialectical relationship: effective involvement in any activity requires a certain level of abilities for this activity, which, in turn, corresponds to the process of development and formation of abilities makes a secret.

depends not only on general mental development and special abilities , which is even understandable from the point of view of intelligence, but also on interests and motives, character traits, temperament, personality orientation, self-awareness, etc. liq.

An important condition for optimizing a person's potential is to pay attention to his activity, a specific type of activity. It is this thing that is extremely important for a person and serves as his motives and goals.

One of the main needs of students is communication. In communication, they study not only others, but also themselves, and acquire the experience of social life. The need for communication helps to establish various relationships,

develop partnerships, friendships, encourages the exchange of knowledge, thoughts, feelings and experiences.

Another important need of the individual is the need for achievement. Student life is unique in terms of opportunities to meet a number of needs. There are certain limitations in meeting their spiritual and material needs. Research data shows that increasing the efficiency of student activity is primarily related to the development of their spiritual needs in accordance with the requirements of studying at a higher educational institution and future profession.

Why do some students work hard and willingly to acquire knowledge and professional skills, and the challenges that arise add strength and enthusiasm to achieve their goals, while others do everything under pressure and fail to achieve any important to The appearance of obstacles sharply reduces their activity. Such differences can be observed in the same external conditions of educational activity (socio-economic situation, organization and methodological support of the educational process, teacher's qualifications, etc.).

In explaining this phenomenon, psychologists and teachers often use individual psychological factors such as students' intelligence level (knowledge, skills, ability to acquire skills and successfully apply them to solve problems), creativity (ability to develop new knowledge) refer to properties; learning motivation, providing a strong positive experience in achieving learning goals, high self-esteem, leading to the formation of high-level claims, etc. But none of these qualities taken separately or even their combination is sufficient to form a student's attitude to daily and hard work in acquiring professional and social competence in the conditions of frequent or long-lasting failures that are inevitable in any complex.

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